

**ВНИМАНИЕ МОЛОДЕЖИ В РАЗВИТИИ НОВОГО
УЗБЕКИСТАНА**

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**ATTENTION TO YOUTH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW
UZBEKISTAN**

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются возможности, предоставляемые молодежи в процессе развития Нового Узбекистана, найти свое место в обществе и стать активным участником формирования гражданского общества.

Ключевые слова: будущие поколения, культура, искусство, спорт, информационные технологии, Защитник Отечества, инновационная деятельность, интеллектуальные игры.

Annotation: This article discusses the opportunities given to young people in the development of New Uzbekistan to find their place in society and become an active participant in the formation of civil society.

Key words: future generations, culture, art, sport, information technology, Defender of the Fatherland, innovative activity, intellectual games.

If we look at the history of the development of developed countries in the world, we can see that these countries have created great opportunities for young people to acquire high education.

In this regard, a number of normative documents adopted by the government indicate that the issue is very serious and urgent. For example, on August 14, 2018, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring

up young people to be spiritually, morally and physically perfect, and to raise the quality of their education system to a new level" is also a clear manifestation of attention to this issue at the state level. In this decision, it is emphasized that the measures aimed at instilling in the minds of the young generation a sense of loyalty to the Motherland and responsibility for its fate, and forming ideological immunity in them against the negative effects of foreign ideas and views, are not effective enough today, and it is clear as a solution to the problem. the development of the program, the need to protect young people from the influence of foreign ideas, to educate them in the spirit of national and universal values, religious tolerance and inter-ethnic harmony at the beginning of this program is justified.

The fact that global information is trying to influence the worldview, thinking, and national-cultural values of our youth in various ways has a positive nature, but it also has the possibility of causing negative consequences. It is important to compare the impact of this process with the "standard" level of positive changes in the life of young people, and on the contrary, to distinguish and take into account the state of its violation. Especially at a time when the scope of information is increasing rapidly, and thanks to independence, our young people have the opportunity to access new information fields, the thoughts and views of a particular nation or people are being disseminated to the whole world through the information system.

Indeed, "Today, when our country has entered a new era of development, our people, especially our children, have love for the Motherland, courage for the future of our country, and the value of a peaceful, free and prosperous life.

strengthening the feeling" has become an urgent issue.

The fate of the reforms implemented in new Uzbekistan and the future of the country are largely related to the social and political activity of young people. "Man, his life, freedom, honor and dignity are supreme a humane democratic state that is considered a value, in terms of building an open and fair society, and realized our high responsibility to the future generations without" the new Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted.

Chapter XIV of the Constitution is devoted to "Family, children and youth". It states that "the state and society should take care of children and young people's commitment to national and universal values, pride in their country and the rich cultural heritage of the people, and the formation of feelings of patriotism and love for the Motherland" (Article 78).

"The state ensures the protection of personal, political, economic, social, cultural and environmental rights of young people, encourages their active participation in the life of society and the state.

State youth intellectual, creative, physical and for moral formation and development, for their education, health care, housing, and work exercise their rights to residence, employment and rest creation of conditions for increase" (Article 79).

As a logical continuation of the work carried out on the basis of the Constitution, the President declared 2024 as the "Year of Youth and Business Support".

It is a fact that does not require proof that young people find their place in society, become an active participant in the formation of civil society, and in many ways, it is related to the creation of laws that protect their interests, ensure their rights and freedoms, and the mechanism of their implementation.

"Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy was adopted during the implementation of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan.

In order to ensure that young people are engaged in modern professions in his "Direction of the state policy on youth", the organization of activities of 1 "Creative Park" in each region, attracting at least 40 thousand young people per year to them, Scientific and to develop the talent of at least 2 million young people by involving them in innovative activities, intellectual games and learning foreign languages, to send 500 talented young people to study at prestigious foreign universities every year, to ensure the employment of 400 thousand young people and it is also intended to achieve the solution of the problems.

The state program on the implementation of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy in the "Year of supporting youth and business" was adopted.

In its paragraph 2, in order to fully realize the potential, talent and initiatives of young people, within the framework of the "Olympiad of Five Initiatives":

Starting from March 1, 2024, in the system of neighborhood, educational institutions, enterprises and organizations, the prize fund in the amount of 600 million soums will be awarded for foreign language competitions ("Children of Ibrat"), cyber sports competitions and intellectual games "Zakovat" organization at the level is indicated.

Within the framework of the state program for the implementation of the "Year of Youth and Business Support", in the framework of the direction of "creating suitable conditions for every person to realize his potential" in 2024:

The knowledge evaluation system of presidential and specialized schools will be introduced in additional 1,000 general secondary educational institutions, and the percentage of practical training in subjects will be increased to 60%.

In its paragraph 6, starting from March 1, 2024:

The practice of directing the funds of the "Yoshlar daftari" fund to the goals of training young people in foreign languages and professions, launching the special platform "Ustoz" for training young people in modern professions, and the initial 250,000 young people will be covered through this platform.

In our country, large-scale work is being carried out in the field of state policy related to youth. In recent years, a special system has been created to support young people in every way, to protect their rights and legal interests, and to educate young people who are able to take responsibility for the future of our country.

The Youth Affairs Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Youth Parliaments under the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis, and the Youth Academy under the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan were established. "Projects Factory" started working in the regions.

Ensuring the healthy growth of the young generation, receiving quality education and growing up as a well-rounded person, as well as comprehensively fostering the interest of young people in culture, art, sports, information technologies and reading books Effective work is being done to introduce "five important initiatives" aimed at support.

On the implementation of the project "One thousand books for young people". we made a separate decision. According to him, starting from next year, the most popular scientific and popular books that encourage our children will be translated into Uzbek and distributed to schools and libraries free of charge.

At the extended meeting of the Security Council, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasized that the role and importance of education in the military-patriotic spirit is increasing in the current extremely complicated conditions, where the struggle for the hearts and minds of the young generation is intensifying. "Today, it is necessary for each of us to become defenders of the Motherland, and to raise our youth in this spirit."

In short, today the scope of opportunities given to young people is expanding. Because they are the creators of our future. The future and development of the country depends on how high their intellectual potential is.

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